

NAVIGATING THE GLOBAL MIGRATION CRISIS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract: *The climate crisis is a long-lasting problem and one of the major issues of this century. The climate crisis directly affects all the creatures on the planet with no variation, from coastal to mountain, land to desert. The amount of greenhouse emissions and the increase in carbon levels cause global warming and ice melting which directly affects the animals and their natural habitats. Furthermore, the world unites together to fight against this major threat. This climate change also affects people's lives, they become climate refugees with no permanent place to live. This paper deals with climate change and the cultural displacement of people.*

Key Words: *Climate Change, Global Warming, Migration, Marine*

Introduction

Humans are the only evolved species on earth who upgrade and obtain knowledge from nature. The revolution in our evolution has made many species extinct. The main causes of major global issues are climate change and global warming. Humans as cultural and social beings tend to protect themselves from various natural calamities, but over one million animals sharing a life thread with humans are under threat. “The temperature increase affects at least 10,967 species on the IUCN Red List and projections suggest that if global temperatures increase by 2°C

by 2100, about 18% of all species on land will face a high risk of going extinct.” It concerns the reality of climate change and its effects.

Climate change and Sea animals

Rising temperatures affect many animals on the planet. Marine creatures are easily affected by climate change. These notable animals are more negatively affected by rising sea temperatures, melting ice, and changing weather patterns caused by climate change, and some have already gone extinct. Golden toads, Coral Chinook salmon, Polar Bears, Adélie penguins, whales, Asian elephants, and sharks. The animals are highly threatened by the rise of climate change, facing habitat loss, decreased food resources, and disrupted reproductive habits. If global temperature rises, more species become vulnerable state of extinction. A study says that global warming is projected to commit over one-third of the Earth’s animal and plant species to extinction by 2050 if current greenhouse gas emissions trajectories continue—a catastrophic loss that would irreversibly reduce biodiversity and alter both ecosystems and human societies across the globe. More than a million species may be at risk of becoming extinct due to global warming.

“The main factors of climate change influencing Europe’s seas are increasing levels of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere rising global temperatures and lower oxygen levels in the water. So far, the ocean globally has absorbed 91% of the heat generated by increased greenhouse gas emissions to the atmosphere, and around 30% of carbon emissions (IPCC, 2021; UNFCCC 2021).”

Climate Migrants

People migrate from place to place on different occasions. Invasion, conquest, colonization and emigration/immigration are such factors for major migration. Due to natural calamities, People are forced to be sent out of their homeland.

“Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, that the greatest single impact of climate change could be on human migration. Millions of people are displaced because of shoreline erosion, coastal flooding and agricultural disruption. Climate change made

a huge impact on every human's life. They are named as climate refugees. Since then various analysts have tried to put numbers on the future flows of climate migrants this would be predicted 200 million in 2050.” (IPCC,1990)

People immigrate over time. Climate-related migration refers to people who decide to leave their homes voluntarily due to the deterioration of their local environment, often due to slow-onset cumulative deforestation, coastal erosion, and others (McAdam, 2010, pp. 10–11). This is not Greek to the people in history, but migrating amid climate change has some serious impact; it led them to another way of life from their natural habits. Displacement based on climate change.

In the last 30 years, the count of storms, droughts, and floods has increased three times. People in developing countries are disproportionately affected, resulting in large-scale migration. Extreme environmental events like hurricanes, tornadoes, and tsunamis are not just headlines; they're serious problems that humanity is facing because of climate change. Migration is not the failing of society; rather, now it's forcefully chasing the native people from their residence, and the people will become unidentified. Eventually, they will miss their cultural identity, their culture, their language, and so on. Climate change is not only the sole threat to the world in general, eventually it will erase all of mankind slowly day by day.

Conclusion

This study aimed to understand the impact and reality behind climate change and migration. Global Warming and climate displacement are now considered significant global challenges. Climate immigrants, both animals and humans, are in a vulnerable state. They are addressing the problem, which the world needs to lend a hand with. It's not a problem for someone; it's a problem for everyone. Humans are the sole responsibility for this major climate change and global warming. The beginning of human betterment is the answer to the suffering of the world. Through this study of climate change, Addressing the issues and challenges of this form of migration will

improve the survival and certain resettlement rights of climate migrants (Miller2017). Addressing these issues of climate change and migration could help people understand the ground reality and a better future for tomorrow.

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